

COMMENCEMENT BAY: RESOURCE-USE CONFLICTS
AT A MARINE SUPERFUND SITE

Edward R. Long

U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
Office of Marine Pollution Assessment
7600 Sand Point Way N.E.
Seattle, Washington 98115

Abstract

Commencement Bay is located at the southern end of the main basin of Puget Sound, a mostly pristine inland sea located in northwestern Washington. Considerable industrial development and modifications of the bay have occurred since the late 1800's. As a result, parts of the bay have become contaminated with numerous heavy metals, synthetic organic compounds, and aromatic hydrocarbons. Many measures of adverse biological effects have accompanied the identification of contaminant "hotspots." Resource-use conflicts have arisen as a result of either actual or perceived consequences of the pollution situation in the bay. These include continued use of the bay for disposal of municipal and industrial wastes; maintenance and extension of navigation channels; expansion of port facilities; maintenance of the health and productivity of marine biota; and utilization (edibility) of seafood. Recent (1980) "Superfund" legislation has made available funds for cleaning up hazardous waste sites throughout the country. Commencement Bay is among the top 10 priority sites designated thus far by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency for this remedial action, the only marine site so ranked. Remedial action for the "site" will be very difficult. It includes deep water dump sites, highly contaminated shallow waterways and tideflats, landfills, and contaminated groundwater. Additional complications will arise due to a poor understanding of the sources of contaminants; their distribution and dynamics; and the relationships, if any, between contaminants and biological disorders in the site.

Introduction

This report reviews recently gathered information on contamination of Commencement Bay, an industrialized marine embayment (Figure 1), and outlines some of the repercussions of this contamination upon resource uses in the bay. The report suggests an approach used in Commencement Bay that is applicable to any industrialized bay for identifying and characterizing contamination problems that warrant remedial action. While many marine embayments in the world probably share contamination and resource-use problems with Commencement Bay, it is unlikely few have been

Figure 1. Commencement Bay and vicinity

studied equally intensively or targeted for equally ambitious clean-up activities.

Economic Development Around the Bay

Indian settlements occupied the shoreline surrounding the bay when the first white immigrants arrived in the 1850's. Beginning in the 1870's, industrial development of the bay led eventually to establishment of saw mills, coal bunkers, wharves, warehouses, grain elevators, boat yards, brick yards, and fisheries-related operations along the Old Tacoma waterfront. A large lead smelter was constructed in 1888 and still exists, now as a copper smelter. Channeling, dredging, and filling of the shoreline at the head of the bay (southeast shore) was begun in the 1880's and continued actively through the 1920's. A series of deep-water parallel waterways provided moorage for deep-draft vessels and resulted in accelerated industrial development of what had been tideflats and marshes. Subsequent dredging and channeling have resulted in the lengthening and deepening of the waterways. Aside from the copper smelter at the mouth of the bay, the majority of the existing industrial facilities are located along these waterways (Dames and Moore, 1981, 1982).

The categories of industries which are now located around the bay include copper smelting, (kraft-process) pulp production, plywood production, primary aluminum reduction, oil refining, pole treating, chlorine and other chemicals production, electroplating, grain storage, metal salvage, boat building and repairing, log storage and loading, food canning, marinas, concrete fabricating, shipping, and seafood processing. The bay has received barge-delivered industrial liquid wastes from chemical manufacturers, dredged material from the waterways, industrial wastewater, municipal sewage, atmospheric fallout of flyash and metals, urban runoff, agricultural runoff, spills of hazardous materials, and seepage of groundwater contaminated with metals and organic chemicals from landfills. Historical dumping and filling along the waterways with metallic smelter slag and leakage of stored hazardous materials have added to the inputs of contaminants to the bay.

Evidence of Contamination

Considerable work has been performed recently by Federal, state, and local agencies to determine the occurrence of chemical contamination problems in Commencement Bay. Much of this research has been performed for NOAA's MESA (Marine Ecosystems Analysis) Puget Sound Project since 1978 as a part of that Project's Sound-wide study of the occurrence, fates, and effects of contaminants. Project-sponsored research in the bay has included: an initial contaminant scan for heavy metals, synthetic organic compounds, and aromatic hydrocarbons; a subsequent detailed chemical characterization for these chemical groups; surveys of adverse biological effects; and measurements of physical and sedimentological processes that influence these contaminants (Long, 1982).

Two types of evidence of contamination are used in this report. The first is based upon direct chemical analyses of sediments, biota, and water samples. The second is based upon observations of adverse biological effects.

Examples of chemical evidence of contamination of the bay are presented in Table 1. Among the areas of Puget Sound that were surveyed, mean concentrations of total aromatic hydrocarbons (AH's), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB's), and lead were highest in sediments from Commencement Bay and Elliott Bay (near Seattle). The mean concentrations of chlorinated butadienes (CBD's) and hexachlorobenzene (HCB) were highest in Commencement Bay. Large variability in contaminant concentrations was found in the bay, though most chemicals were highly concentrated in the waterways and along the Old Tacoma shoreline (Malins et al., 1982). The Hylebos Waterway had high levels of PCB's and CBD's in sediments and water, especially at its mouth (Riley et al., 1981). Many sediment samples from the bay had hundreds of organic compounds. Special attempts to identify some of them revealed quantifiable levels of about 250 compounds. They included:

chlorinated isomers of benzenes, hexadienes, styrenes, pentenes, naphthalenes, fluoranthenes, and ethanes; alkenyl benzenes; methyl fluorenes; and numerous polar compounds (Malins et al., 1982).

Chemical analyses of biota tissues have shown high levels of some contaminants (Table 1), particularly chlorinated organic compounds, but those for edible tissue have not exceeded U.S. Food and Drug Administration limits. However, there are no standards for the majority of the compounds found.

Along with the chemical analyses, considerable work has been performed to gather biological evidence of adverse effects, if any, of exposure to the contaminant suites that exist throughout the Sound. Field sampling, laboratory bioassays and other tests, field experiments, and observations have been performed. High frequencies of lesions in bottomfish and crabs, mortality in amphipods and oyster embryos, depressed respiration rates in oligochaetes, high mutation rates in fish cells, depressed colonization rates in epibenthos, and depressed infauna species richness have been demonstrated (Table 2). The parts of the bay where the strongest biological responses were measured coincide with those found to be chemical "hotspots."

Overall, the chemical and biological evidence gathered thus far indicate that water, biota, and sediments in the bay are contaminated with a wide variety of chemicals and that adverse biological effects at the subcellular, cellular, histologic, organism, and assemblage levels can be demonstrated as either a consequence of exposure to samples of water and sediment from the bay or among in situ samples of biota living in the bay. However, the specific relationships between demonstrated effects and chemicals is largely unknown.

Resource-Use Conflicts

Some of the major resource use conflicts that have arisen as a consequence of new information on contamination problems are summarized in Table 3. Possible alternatives for resolving the conflicts are suggested.

Channel maintenance dredging in the industrial waterways is necessary to prevent shoaling and impediment of maritime traffic. However, the sediments in the waterways are among the most contaminated in the bay. The possibilities exist for adverse biological effects in addition to those already demonstrated by resuspension of sediment-bound contaminants during dredging and disposal of dredged material. Conflicts have arisen, then, between commercial uses of the waterways for a growing Pacific-rim port and minimizing potential for adverse biological effects.

Numerous private and governmental activities involving commercial development of shorelands, filling of waterways, and construction of piers, marinas, and dikes are planned for parts of the bay. Since these activities may remobilize

Table 1. Measures of chemical contamination and results noted from Commencement Bay. (Data from Malins et al., 1982; Riley et al., 1980, 1981; John Osborn, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, personal communication)

Measure of Contamination	Results from Commencement Bay	Possible Sources
Chlorinated butadienes	Found in suspended matter and water; up to 20,000 ppb dry wt. in sediments; up to 9,100 ppb dry wt. in sole livers; mean conc. in bay sediments exceeds means for reference areas by 213x to 800x	Chemical production; discharged and dumped
Polychlorinated biphenyls	Found in suspended matter and water; up to 1,200 ppb dry wt. in sediments; 28,000 ppb dry wt. in crab hepatopancreas; up to 20,000 ppb dry wt. in sole livers; up to 27,000 ppb wet wt. in cod livers	Spills, leaks, dumping of PCB's
Lead	Up to 790 ppm dry wt. in sediments; up to 396 ppm dry wt. in suspended matter	Gasoline exhaust, marine paints, runoff
Arsenic	Up to 470 ppm dry wt. in sediments; 106 ppm dry wt. in suspended matter; 66,000 µg/l in storm drain water entering bay	Atmospheric, liquid, and solid slag inputs
Aromatic hydrocarbons	Total of up to 57 ppm dry wt. of 27 compounds in surface sediments, up to 17 ppm dry wt. in worms; total of up to 105 ppm dry wt. of 18 compounds in subsurface sediments	Combustion products, petroleum spills, industrial effluents, highway runoff

sediment-bound contaminants and/or become sources of additional contaminants, conflicts may arise between efforts to further develop the bay and efforts to decrease its contamination levels.

Given that sediments, biota, and water in the bay are known to be contaminated, opportunities for the continued or expanded use of the bay as a receiving system for wastes may be diminished. Conflicts may arise between efforts to decrease contaminant levels in the bay and the needs of dischargers to dispose of wastes inexpensively.

The concentrations of individual chemicals in edible seafood tissues from the bay apparently do not exceed Federal standards, though they are generally higher than those from nearby reference areas in the Sound. However, there are no standards for mixtures of chemicals, nor for the majority of them found in the biota from the bay. Some 50-60 people fish in the bay per day; 10 and 50 percent fish there on a daily and weekly basis, respectively. About 95 percent of the fish that are caught are consumed (Doug Pierce, Tacoma-Pierce County Health Department, personal communication). Conflicts have arisen between the desires (and needs) of people to catch fish for consumption and the possibilities of adverse health effects. In addition, the perceived negative aspects of consuming contaminated and

"sick" fish (those with histopathological disorders) may result in loss of income to those businesses selling fishing equipment and services to fewer fishermen.

The nearshore sediments and waters of the bay serve as habitat and nursery areas for numerous fish and invertebrates, including migrating juvenile salmon. These fish spend one to two months feeding upon epibenthic zooplankton and other prey in the bay before starting their journey to the Pacific Ocean. Though effects of the contaminants in the bay upon salmon are unknown, these fish are exposed directly to chemicals in the water and their prey. They also encounter altered prey availability, as indicated by sediment bioassay and infauna community data. Conflicts arise, then, between efforts to maintain or increase salmon runs and the possible repercussions of existing contaminants in the bay.

"Superfund" Activities

The Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation and Liability Act (CERCLA), or "Superfund," was enacted in December 1980. It authorized Federal action in cleaning up hazardous waste spills, sites, and releases. As a part of its responsibilities in implementing the Superfund program, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency

Table 2. Field and laboratory measures of adverse biological effects and results noted from Commencement Bay

Measures of Adverse Biological Effects	Results from Commencement Bay	Reference(s)
Liver lesions in English sole	Significantly higher frequency of disease than mean for Sound-wide study area	Malins et al., 1980, 1982
Midgut and hepatopancreas lesions in crabs	Higher frequency than at reference areas	Malins et al., 1982
Amphipod bioassays with sediments	High mortality rates, especially in parts of waterways	Swartz et al., 1982
Oligochaete respiration rate tests with sediments	Respiration significantly lower at many sites than mean for Sound-wide study area	Chapman et al. (in press)
Fish cell anaphase aberration tests	Mutation rate significantly higher at many sites than mean for Sound-wide study area	Chapman et al. (in press)
96-hour oyster embryo bioassays with water	High percent mortalities and abnormalities at some sites in waterways	Joseph Cummins, U.S. EPA, Personal Communication
Colonization rates of artificial substrates	Depressed rates (species number versus time) relative to reference areas after 12 months	Schoener (in press)
Taxon richness of sediment infauna	2-3 taxa in Hylebos Waterway versus 10-11 taxa in reference areas	Malins et al., 1982

(EPA) on October 23, 1981 designated 114 sites targeted for remedial action. The sites were ranked in tiers of tens by means of a hazard ranking system, which weighed potential for human health and environmental effects. Commencement Bay was ranked in the top tier, the only marine site thus ranked. As a result of this action, considerable activity has taken place in formulating a remedial action plan for Commencement Bay (U.S. EPA/WDOE/T-PCHD, 1982).

Planning a "fix" for Commencement Bay will likely be very difficult because of the complex situation there and a poor understanding of what to fix. The site includes a variety of problems: well water and groundwater contamination, landfills, nearshore and deep water dump sites. On-site treatment (an intent of Superfund) would be impractical for the deep water dump areas. The distributions of many contaminants are independent of each other and poorly defined. The relationships, if any, between contaminants and adverse biological effects is unknown. Thus, there is no way to know which chemicals present the worst ecologic problems and, thus, should be removed. It is also difficult to estimate the decrease in contaminant levels that must be attained to assure

"safe" conditions for humans and the marine ecosystem. The locations and chemistry of landfills near the bay and the rates and flow patterns of leachates from them into groundwater are poorly understood. The importance of existing sources, if any, and their relationship to historical sources, is mostly unknown. Thus, the plan to "fix" Commencement Bay is actually a plan to define the problem such that the engineering or regulatory options that may effect the "fix" can be weighed and planned. Following this problem-definition stage, a combination of remedies such as the following may be possible: capping of deep dump sites with clean material, dredging of nearshore areas with upland disposal, diversion and treatment of groundwater, stopping or treating discharges, and advising human avoidance.

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Table 3. Resource-use conflicts resulting from existing contamination of the bay and possible alternatives for resolving them

Consequences of Bay Contamination	Conflicts (Real or Perceived)	Alternatives for Resolution
Contaminated sediments	Channel maintenance	Bury or cap with "clean" material
	Dredged material disposal	Remove to upland and contain
	Port facility expansion	Treat or detoxify
	Continued use of water body as receptor for discharges	Decrease waterway use, limit port expansion
Contaminated consumable biota	Utilization (consumption) of resource	Close fishery
	Maintenance of fisheries stocks	Remove pollutant reservoir
	Maintenance of fishermen's interest	Inform public
	Continued use of water body as receptor for discharges	
Contaminated nonconsumed biota	Ecosystem assimilative capacity exceeded for contaminant(s)	Remove pollutant reservoir
	Maintenance of prey populations for consumable fisheries	
	Continued use of water body as receptor for discharges	
Contaminated water	Continued discharge of pollutants precluded	Control source(s)
	Maintenance of aesthetic quality	Pretreat influents
Diseased biota	Utilization of biota	Inform public
	Maintenance of stocks	Remove pollutant reservoir
	Maintenance of fishermen's interest	

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